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Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Employee Outcomes in the Aviation Industry during the COVID- 19 Pandemic Era. A Conceptual Framework

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ABSTRACT

Purpose – By drawing on conservation of resources, social identity and attachment theories, this paper investigates the impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives on work engagement, covid-induced perceived job insecurity and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). The mediating role of organizational pride and trust is also explored. **Relevance** – The pandemic has caused an unimaginable collapse of air passenger and cargo volumes, sweeping job cuts and huge financial losses for aviation. Employees in the aviation industry have been afflicted by the pandemic but also decipher CSR and are part of the road towards recovery combined with responsible business practices. **Methodology** – An integrative literature review method was adopted. A range of literature review relevant to the concept and the materialization of CSR, both generally and specifically in the aviation industry, is explored. A conceptual model linking CSR to certain employee outcomes is then proposed and discussed. **Findings** – The paper offers insights into the ways CSR initiatives may impact employees in the aviation industry at the emotional, attitudinal and behavioral level during the pandemic. It is proposed that when companies undertake CSR activities, employees develop higher levels of organizational trust and pride particularly reinforced by empathetic leadership and employee CSR participation. Those emotions, in turn, lead to more engaged employees with reduced feelings of job insecurity. An improvement in employees' OCB is considered to be the end result. **Practical implications** – This study is helpful for companies within the aviation industry, during the pandemic and post-pandemic era, to plan and implement CSR activities in such a way that could positively affect employee outcomes.

Keywords: *Corporate Social Responsibility, Covid-19, Aviation Industry, Employee Outcomes*

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Introduction

Overview of the CSR concept

The corporate social responsibility (CSR) construct was first defined by Bowen in the 1950s (Bowen, 1953). Since then, owing to contextuality, additional definitions were proposed such as that of Carroll according to which CSR refers to “*the economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic expectations that society has of organizations at a given point in time*” (Carroll, 1979, p.500).

Freeman introduced the term ‘stakeholders’ to distinguish the parties which affect and are affected by an organization other than its shareholders (Freeman, 1984). Stakeholder theory is based on the premise that success for businesses is reached via strong long-term relationships with its stakeholders (De Roeck et al., 2014). Stakeholders can be classified into societal, economic and organizational or into primary and secondary (Haski-Leventhal, 2018).

Stakeholders can also be categorized into internal and external based on whether they have a direct affiliation to the company or not (De Chernatony & Harris, 2000). Based on this categorization, initiatives directed towards internal stakeholders, such as employees, constitute internal CSR whereas activities which benefit external stakeholders, such as the environment or consumers, are included in external CSR (Turker, 2009).

A narrow view of the concept of CSR has yielded to a broader consideration of CSR issues resulting in strategic CSR which was defined by the European Commission as the voluntary integration of ethical, social and environmental concerns into the core strategy and business operations of companies (Roszkowska-Menkes, 2018). Sustainability, business ethics, corporate citizenship, creating shared value, corporate responsibility and other similar terms have been used as alternative concepts to CSR (Haski-Leventhal, 2018).

In our study, possible outcomes of internal CSR will be discussed. At this point, it is imperative that we emphasize the importance of employees within the CSR concept. Employees constitute a key stakeholder group in the implementation of CSR especially in the service sector as they materialize CSR by means of various activities and finally communicate it to customers (Asante Boadi et al., 2019). Employee perceptions of CSR have been found to more effectively predict CSR-related employee outcomes and are therefore considered more reliable than CSR reports (Kim et al., 2021).

Overall, firm engagement in CSR was linked to several individual and organizational positive outcomes such as job satisfaction, commitment, engagement, trust and pride as well as organizational identification, extra-role performance, firm performance, customer satisfaction and competitive advantage (Asante Boadi et al., 2019; Bhatia, 2012; Kim et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2018; Newman et al., 2015; Porter & Kramer, 2002). Despite the wide variety of factors studied as CSR outcomes, literature mainly focused on macro-CSR that is how CSR impacts the firm. Research on micro-CSR, on the other hand, concentrates on how individual stakeholders react to CSR and has mostly examined how CSR is received by customers (Boğan & Dedeoğlu, 2020; Chen & Khuangga, 2021). Deeper investigation of micro-CSR and most importantly of the

mechanisms via which CSR impacts individual stakeholders is deemed necessary (Kim et al., 2021).

CSR, aviation industry and COVID-19

Aviation is a new industry but has come a long way since 1903 when the first sustained powered flight took place (McManners, 2016). It belongs to the service industry and shares some common features with the manufacturing industry (Clancy, 2002). It is also closely related with, supports and is supported by the tourism industry (Serhan et al., 2018). Actors within the aviation industry operate in a highly competitive market also distinguished for its vulnerable financial health (Fitzgerald & Cooper, 2018). Nevertheless, the industry has shown resilience in the face of previous crises.

The oil crisis, terrorist attacks and armed conflicts, economic crises and outbreaks of serious diseases, in the past, had created a cascading effect throughout the aviation industry. As of late 2019, measures and restrictions established to contain COVID-19 have led to a sharp decrease in air connectivity. Flights were cancelled, aircraft were grounded, employees were laid-off. At the same time, aviation must deal with the competition from rail services and the rise of video conferencing which are viewed as 'greener' alternatives for travelling by air (Suau-Sanchez et al., 2020; Tsunoda, 2018; Wynes et al., 2019).

The environmental impact of aviation has been generally recognized in the past (Holden, 2004). Companies engage in CSR activities amid surging expectations for more transparency in business management and operations (CSR Europe, 2020). The Paris Agreement and European Green Deal have pushed sustainability in aviation to the top of the political agenda (European Regions Airline Association, 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic has spurred the implementation of CSR initiatives in the aviation sector. According to CSR Europe (2020), roughly 90% of the people asked in a global survey consider the problem of climate change as urgent as COVID-19.

The specific objective of this study is to explore the relationships between employee perceptions of CSR and a number of emotional, attitudinal and behavioral outcomes, namely organizational trust and pride, job insecurity, work engagement and organizational citizenship behavior. The moderating role -if any- of the empathetic leadership style and employee CSR participation is also examined. The study focused on the aviation industry during the COVID-19 era due to the highly internationalized environment in which companies in this industry operate thereby maximizing any CSR outcomes and the significant effect that COVID-19 had on employees within the industry. Based on all the above, the rest of the paper is structured as follows: the research method adopted in this study will be discussed in the next section followed by an analysis of the proposed framework. The fourth section presents the theoretical support of the proposed model while the discussion and conclusion part summarize the main issues discussed.

Methodology

This paper reviews the databased literature on employee outcomes of CSR activities. An integrative review of extant literature on the topic was conducted to identify potential links between CSR activities and employee emotional, attitudinal and

behavioral reactions. Critical research questions and conceptual gaps were detected and studied. An integrative literature review examines, critiques and synthesizes, in an integrated way, representative literature on a topic while generating new knowledge (Balon, 2020; Torraco, 2005).

The first step was to formulate the research question guiding the study. The focus of this integrative literature review is on CSR employee outcomes in the aviation industry during the COVID-19 pandemic era. Consequently, a list of crucial factors relevant to CSR activities, employees, CSR in the aviation industry and COVID-19 was compiled and explored. A conceptual model which may explain how CSR impacts employees in the aviation industry during the pandemic is proposed. Theories and findings which could contribute to the interpretation of the proposed relationships are presented in the following sections.

According to Torraco (2005), integrative literature reviews address either mature topics or emerging ones. The responsibility of businesses within the aviation industry is not a new topic; however, employee outcomes of CSR initiatives have not been generally explored, not least in the aviation sector. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has created an entirely new ‘normal’, both unforeseen and unfamiliar to the world. It could, therefore, be argued that this integrative literature review looks into another aspect of a well-known subject within an unprecedented context.

Proposed Framework

The ‘PLANE’ model

The proposed framework of this study, also referred to as the ‘PLANE’ model is illustrated in Figure 1. Based on the ‘PLANE model, it is suggested that perceptions of employees about their organization’s involvement in CSR activities will affect their work engagement as well as the level of job insecurity caused by the pandemic. Organizational trust and organizational pride are proposed as the underlying mechanisms via which employee perceptions of CSR might impact on job insecurity and work engagement. Additionally, the extent of employee participation in those activities and empathy shown by their leaders are expected to moderate the link between perceptions of CSR and organizational trust and pride of employees. Finally, according to the model, employees’ organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) could be affected by both work engagement and job insecurity.

This conceptual framework views employees’ OCB as being indirectly influenced by the CSR activities of the firm. Specifically, employee perceptions of their organization’s CSR involvement may produce higher levels of organizational trust and pride thus affecting their work engagement and job insecurity, in a positive and negative manner, respectively. Feelings of organizational trust/pride could be enhanced by empathetic leadership and employee participation in their firm’s CSR actions. This process could lead to increased employee OCB.

Figure 1: The ‘PLANE’ model

Overview of the main study concepts

Employee perceptions of CSR

In this study, employee perceptions are used to measure CSR. Questions may arise as to whether a more objective measure of CSR should have been deployed. However, based on stakeholder theory and the resource-based view, the importance of employees in the business operations of an organization is manifested via multiple ways. Employees constitute the inimitable attributes of an organization and, consequently, a source of competitive advantage (Park et al., 2018). Employees also play an important role in service delivery due to their immediate interaction with customers (Brammer, Millington, & Rayton, 2007).

Factoring in the subjective view of employees regarding CSR initiatives was deemed as contributing to a more realistic CSR measurement as it reflects how CSR is embedded in the organization (Asante Boadi et al., 2019). Previous studies confirmed that a subjective approach on CSR issues can better predict work-related outcomes (De Roeck & Maon, 2016; Tafolli & Grabner-Krauter, 2020).

Organizational pride

Organizational pride is related to feelings of self-respect and pleasure resulting from organizational membership (Jones, 2010). Pride can be either personal or collective, either authentic or vanity in disguise (Durrah et al., 2021). Employee organizational pride can emerge from a specific event related to the firm or a from a generalized view of the organization (Goudarzi et al., 2011).

Organizational pride has been linked to both positive and negative outcomes. Employee and customer satisfaction along with employee retention and determination have been found to be related with organizational pride (Farooq & Salam, 2021; Fiernaningsih et al., 2019). Research has also provided support for the claim that employees’ personal judgment about how well they are able to execute courses of action

necessary in order to handle future situations is boosted by feelings of organizational pride (Williams & De Steno, 2008). Contrastingly, organizational pride may lead to negativity and work-related stress (Durrah et al., 2021).

Organizational trust

Trust usually develops within a context of uncertainty (Serrano-Archimi et al., 2018). Trust corresponds to the feeling of being vulnerable towards the actions of another individual whom you cannot control but expect that will perform in a certain favorable way (Mayer et al., 1995). Organizational trust has been found to increase job satisfaction, co-operation and work engagement while also leading to fewer turnover intentions (Serrano-Archimi et al., 2018; Holland et al., 2017).

Empathetic leadership

Empathy denotes an emotional understanding of another individual's feelings but also encompasses feelings of security and emotional support provided to the individual to whom empathy is shown (Kock et al., 2019). Leadership goes far beyond management (Barker, 2001). Empathetic leadership is a leadership style characterized by the leader's ability to identify the followers' feelings and provide emotional support (Bani-Melhem et al., 2020).

A business environment brims with risks and uncertainty thereby making a leader's empathetic approach towards their followers beneficial for both the individuals and the organization (Kock et al., 2019). Research on empathetic leadership has not been exhaustive however findings provide support for a link between empathetic leadership and job satisfaction and extra-role performance (Bani-Melhem et al., 2020).

Employee CSR participation

Employee CSR participation refers to the involvement and active participation of employees in CSR initiatives and occurs via different ways such as employee volunteering, payroll giving or employee-led CSR (Haski-Leventhal, 2018; Kim et al., 2010). Employee participation in CSR activities should not be confused with employee perceptions of CSR (Im et al., 2017). The role of employees in CSR participation goes beyond just merely executing such kind of initiatives to having a say by suggesting CSR policies (Kim et al., 2010).

CSR participation can foster specific talents and skills of employees while also making CSR activities more visible (Haski-Leventhal, 2018). Additionally, by involving employees into CSR initiatives, a firm creates a strong organizational culture of responsibility, sustainability and caring (Haski-Leventhal, 2018). Employee participation is related with increased extra-role performance (Supanti & Butcher, 2018), job satisfaction, organizational identification and commitment (Im et al., 2017; Kim et al., 2010) and engagement (Brammer et al., 2007). Congruence between the socially responsible identity and behavior of employees, and the organization can produce optimum results (Haski-Leventhal, 2018; Kim et al., 2010).

Work engagement

Work engagement has been defined as the opposite construct of burnout (Maslach et al., 2001). Work engagement is a “*positive, fulfilling work-related state of mind*” characterized by vigor, absorption and dedication (Schaufeli et al., 2006, p. 792). It, therefore, corresponds to high energy levels, full concentration and strong identification with work from the part of employees while at work (Schaufeli et al., 2002).

Engaged employees yield positive results at both the individual and organizational level. Personal well-being, innovation, productivity, organizational commitment, extra-role performance and firm reputation have been proven to be associated with work engagement (De Clercq et al., 2014; Park et al., 2018). Conversely, disengaged employees can cost an organization in terms of performance, productivity, extra monitoring processes and turnover (Mostafa et al., 2020).

Job insecurity caused by the COVID-19 pandemic

Job insecurity can be described as the perception of a potential job loss against the will of the job holder (Vander Elst et al., 2014). The concept of job insecurity became a popular topic for researchers in the 1980s (Vander Elst et al., 2014). Based on the definition of job insecurity, it is concluded that it is both a subjective and involuntary experience linked to uncertainty (Wang et al., 2015). Organizational, socio-political and individual characteristics can moderate feelings of job insecurity. The way employees are treated by their company, social policy practices in place and certain personality traits influence how individuals perceive job insecurity (Hipp, 2020; Wang et al., 2015). Job insecurity outcomes have been studied at a personal and organizational level. Employee health and well-being have proven to be negatively affected (Gasparro et al., 2020). Decreased engagement, commitment and job satisfaction also ensue from feelings of job insecurity (Di Stefano, 2020). Interestingly, job satisfaction is associated with an organization’s difficulty to retain its staff (Richter et al., 2020).

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB)

The concept of organizational citizenship originates in the 1930s (Ocampo et al., 2018). OCB is an extra-role behavior (Ocampo et al., 2018). It is a non-compulsory behavior regulated by an individual’s judgement. Extra-role behaviors are not formally rewarded but do contribute to an advancement in the way the organization works (Organ, 1988). At least forty different types of organizational citizenship behaviors have been detected (Dagenais-Cooper & Paillé, 2012). Several definitions of OCB exist in literature. The idea of such behaviors being non-critical yet beneficial to the organization constitutes common ground among scholars whereas other aspects, such as the lack of a formal reward, are questioned (Lee & Allen, 2002).

Advantages regarding the individual and the organization brought about by employee OCB are effectiveness, efficiency, productivity, fewer turnover intentions and enhanced competitive advantage (Ocampo et al., 2018; Jehanzeb, 2020). The concept of OCB is highly contextual. Thus, research is deemed necessary to clarify the existence of potential antecedents and outcomes thereof.

Theoretical Support of the Proposed Model

Employee perceptions of corporate social responsibility and organizational pride/organizational trust

Based on social identity theory employees in firms which implement CSR initiatives tend to be prouder (El Akremi et al., 2018). More specifically, companies which engage in such kind of activities are usually more reputable. Employees who identify themselves with their organization are expected to feel prouder when the latter is connected to a more responsible stance (John et al., 2019). Organizational pride results from both external and internal CSR however the former more intensely triggers feelings of pride (Jia et al., 2019).

Trust has been portrayed as a primary and immediate outcome of CSR (Pivato et al., 2008). CSR activities have been found to improve the quality of the relationship between the organization and the employees by means of increasing trust (Park et al., 2018; Serrano-Archimi et al., 2018). The mediating role of trust in the relationship between CSR and several employee and organizational outcomes has been studied, thus, highlighting the importance of trust as a prominent mechanism via which CSR impacts employees and the firm (Serrano-Archimi et al., 2018). As a result we suggest that:

Hypothesis 1: Employee perceptions of CSR positively affect organizational pride.

Hypothesis 2: Employee perceptions of CSR positively affect organizational trust.

Employee Perceptions of CSR, empathetic leadership and organizational pride/trust

Possible results stemming from the interaction of empathetic leadership and organizational pride have barely been examined (Lythreath et al., 2019). Even more, empathetic leadership has not been largely studied within the concept of CSR and sustainability (Bani-Melhem et al., 2020). Despite this, research on empathetic language revealed that it entails feelings of pride (Yue et al., 2020). In this paper, we propose that empathetic leadership will enhance feelings of organizational pride. Based on conservation of resources theory, empathy shown by leader towards followers may act against any depletion of resources that everyday work and personal life sometimes result in.

Empathetic leadership has been found to generate emotional ties between the leader and the followers (Kock et al., 2019). Showing empathy and conveying psychological support has overall been viewed as providing psychological safety (Bani-Melhem, 2020). In this study, empathetic leadership is proposed to reinforce organizational trust. Social exchange theory is guided by the premise of reciprocity which entails the interchange of mutually favorable actions (Kath et al., 2010). Such social exchanges may regulate the relationship between perceived CSR and trust. Our hypotheses are formulated as follows:

Hypothesis 3: Empathetic leadership will enhance feelings of organizational pride resulting from employee perceptions of CSR.

Hypothesis 4: Empathetic leadership will enhance feelings of organizational trust resulting from employee perceptions of CSR.

Employee Perceptions of CSR, employee CSR participation and organizational pride/trust

As argued above, companies which engage in CSR activities are considered more responsible and prestigious. Based on social identity theory, participation in such initiatives is expected to facilitate the identification of employees with their organization and boost their feelings of pride (Jones, 2010; Kim et al., 2010). Haski-Leventhal (2018) contends that CSR participation leads to employee engagement by increasing employees' organizational pride, enthusiasm for their firm and affective commitment.

Yilmaz et al., (2015) also found that higher level of employee pride is developed via their involvement in CSR activities. Based on self-determination theory, we expect that employee CSR participation will moderate the relationship between employee CSR participation and organizational pride. Self-determination theory propounds the existence of three basic psychological needs essential for human development and thriving: the need for autonomy, relatedness and competence (Hu et al., 2019). By participating in CSR initiatives, employees further have a say in the organization for CSR initiatives (Kim et al., 2010) and their skills and talents are strengthened (Haski-Leventhal, 2018; Kumar et al., 2020). Thus, the aforementioned psychological needs are fulfilled.

Employee CSR participation leads employees to a better understanding of CSR practices (Supanti & Butcher, 2018). In this way, employees not only realize that their organization engages in responsible initiatives but also view such actions as deriving from the culture and values of the organization rather than from external pressure (Chen & Hung-Baesecke, 2014).

Based on cue consistency theory, we expect that employee CSR participation will enhance the positive relationship between employee perceptions of CSR and organizational trust. The main premise of cue consistency theory is that individuals rely on various signals within their environment and evaluate the consistency of those signals to determine what kind of attitudes and behaviors to display (Peng et al., 2020). We, therefore, argue that employee participation in the CSR initiatives undertaken by their companies will contribute to the consistency of cues conveying the message of a responsible organization thereby creating a positive bias related to trust towards the company.

Hypothesis 5: Employee CSR participation will enhance feelings of organizational pride resulting from employee perceptions of CSR.

Hypothesis 6: Employee CSR participation will enhance feelings of organizational trust resulting from employee perceptions of CSR.

Organizational pride and work engagement/job insecurity

The theoretical framework underpinning the positive relationship between organizational pride and work engagement is premised on social identity theory and conservation of resources theory. Jia et al. (2019) found that CSR initiatives towards a firm's external stakeholders elicit pride which, in turn, leads to increased work engagement. This could be explained by the fact that employees identify themselves

with their organization (Shahzadi et al., 2019); hence, more responsible and prestigious organizations are likely to have prouder employees. Moreover, according to conservation of resources theory, organizational pride functions as an extra resource for employees thereby protecting them from any negative work-related issues and preventing disengagement.

The COVID-19 pandemic has intensified feelings of job insecurity which are normally inherent in any work environment. The effect of pride in an uncertain work context has not been extensively explored. Instead of organizational pride, pride in the job has received some attention, however, findings on its role remain inconsistent (Pate et al., 2003). Research distinguishes among three factors which determine the level of perceived job insecurity: i) individual characteristics, ii) organizational characteristics and iii) awareness of social policies against unemployment (Hipp, 2020). Moreover, Hipp (2020) concluded that the presence of a comparison group in higher risk pushed employees to evaluate their own situation as more positive. Based on the effect of a relative position, we suggest that prouder employees will experience less job insecurity.

Hypothesis 7: Organizational pride positively affects work engagement.

Hypothesis 8: Organizational pride negatively affects job insecurity caused by COVID-19.

Organizational trust and work engagement/job insecurity

CSR has been recorded among the main antecedents of organizational trust (De Clercq et al., 2014; Memon, Ghani, & Khalid, 2020). The positive link between organizational trust and work engagement is grounded in social exchange theory, attachment theory and conservation of resources theory. Reciprocating the positive feelings of trust can result in more engaged employees while trust may not only shield employees against unpleasant developments but also prompt positive work outcomes. Moreover, in line with attachment theory, trust may facilitate the creation of emotional bonds between the organization and its employees. When those bonds are stabilized, employee work engagement is expected to rise.

Research has mostly focused on the insecurity-trust relationship rather than the link between trust and job insecurity. Trust dampens the negative impact of job insecurity; at the same time, when trust declines feelings of job insecurity worsen (Jiang & Probst, 2019; Pate et al., 2003). We deploy conservation of resources theory to explicate how organizational trust may alleviate the psychological strain caused by job insecurity in the pandemic era.

Hypothesis 9: Organizational trust positively affects work engagement.

Hypothesis 10: Organizational trust negatively affects job insecurity caused by COVID-19.

Work engagement and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB)

The direct relationship between work engagement and OCB has been examined in previous studies. Findings provide evidence for a positive association between the two variables. Vigor, dedication and absorption are the main characteristics which describe work engagement (Schaufeli et al., 2006). From a conservation of resources theory and

an attachment theory perspective, work engagement composed by those attributes is expected to provide employees with the necessary resources and emotional ties and, consequently, positively influence their OCB.

Research has confirmed the positive effect of work engagement on employee organizational citizenship behavior. Huang et al. (2019), Rurkkhum and Bartlett (2012) and Urbini et al. (2020) studied how work engagement impacts extra-role behavior. Different components and types of OCB have been included in research leading to converging results in favor of a positive link between the two constructs. Thus, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 11: Work engagement positively affects employee OCB.

Job insecurity caused by COVID-19 and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB)

Results on the causal role of job insecurity have varied. Job insecurity has been linked to reduced job satisfaction and less employee retention but research has not been able to establish how job insecurity impacts employee performance (Armstrong-Stassen et al., 2001; Wang et al., 2015). Job insecurity has generally been found to be negatively related with OCB yet disparities can be attributed to the subjective and contextual nature of the latter (Kumar et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2015).

Di Stefano et al. (2020) and Vander Elst et al. (2014) employed the psychological contract theory to provide an explanation about how job insecurity may influence OCB. Psychological contract theory has been positioned between broader theories, such as social exchange theory, and theories regarding specific constructs, such as organizational commitment (Montes et al., 2015). In this case, job insecurity may be viewed by employees as a “*failure to fulfill psychological contract obligation*” otherwise referred to as a ‘psychological contract breach’ resulting in negative outcomes for the employees and the firm (Montes et al., 2015, p. 1). Hence, it is suggested that:

Hypothesis 12: Job insecurity caused by COVID-19 negatively affects employee OCB.

Discussion and Conclusions

Despite extensive research on macro-CSR, the micro-foundations of CSR remain uncharted especially when employees are concerned. The process via which CSR impacts employees’ emotions, attitudes and behaviors has not been clarified. CSR has evolved from a narrow concept to an overarching theme and a societal expectation that goes around the world. Alongside the successful achievements of the aviation industry lie the operational repercussions of companies within the sector. It is argued that aviation is one of the most difficult industries for the application of sustainability (McManners, 2016). However, CSR can boost sustainability in aviation especially when it is implemented in a strategic manner (Serhan et al., 2018).

The role of employees in the materialization of CSR-related goals has been highlighted since they convert those goals into real actions. CSR affects not only the firm but also its employees. COVID-19 has caused a massive disruption in the life and work of a lot of people around the world. People employed in companies in the aviation

industry have been severely affected by the pandemic. It is, thus, important to study whether CSR activities could benefit them.

The ‘PLANE’ model proposes that perceived CSR ultimately affects extra-role behavior of employees. The path that may lead to this implies the creation of feelings of pride for and trust towards the organization which are regulated by empathetic leadership and the extent to which employees are involved in CSR activities. Subsequently, work engagement of employees may rise and feelings of job insecurity may fade away. Finally, employees who are more engaged and less insecure of their jobs react with higher level of OCB.

The purpose of this paper has been limited to proposing a theoretical framework to explain how CSR initiatives could impact employees in a rather uncertain time period. Relevant literature has been reviewed. Nevertheless, the COVID-19 pandemic has created a wholly new context which may affect actual results. Research is needed to examine if the proposed framework is applicable to employees in the aviation industry and if results can be generalized to other industries and other cultural contexts.

This paper adds to the body of literature on micro-CSR. Additionally, it provides a theoretical model which could explain the mechanisms via which CSR affects employees. There is no clear answer regarding the end of the COVID-19 pandemic. That intensifies the uncertainty which is inherent in most crises. That also provides a unique backdrop against which this study was conducted.

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Conflict of Interests

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